

THE INNOVATE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR
AT SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7534588>

ELSEVIER

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Abstract: Most English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students in secondary school find it difficult to learn English grammar. Innovative ideas, interesting teaching materials, practising and drilling students for English grammar should all be done in a fun and joyful manner. The primary goal of this library research was to find and describe examples of practical grammar instruction methods in an EFL that used innovative methodologies. The library-based research process entails identifying and locating relevant information, analysing what has been discovered, and then developing and expressing ideas. The findings revealed that songs and poems, music, games, and tasks can all be used as classroom tools. Using innovative methodologies in teaching English grammar in secondary school classrooms has paved the way for students to learn the language meaningfully.

Keywords: innovative techniques, teaching English grammar, secondary schools.

Received: 12-01-2023

Accepted: 13-01-2023

Published: 22-01-2023

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Abstract: Большинство учащихся, изучающих английский язык как иностранный (EFL) в средней школе, испытывают трудности с изучением английской грамматики. Инновационные идеи, интересные учебные материалы, практика и обучение студентов английской грамматике должны проходить в веселой и радостной манере. Основная цель этого библиотечного исследования состояла в том, чтобы найти и описать примеры практических методов обучения грамматике в EFL, в которых использовались инновационные методологии. Исследовательский процесс в библиотеке включает в себя выявление и обнаружение соответствующей информации, анализ того, что было обнаружено, а затем разработку и выражение идей

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Introduction

Grammar classes in secondary schools have the terrible reputation of being tedious. They rely on traditional techniques of presenting, such as textbooks and broad fill-in-the-blanks tasks. Grammar study mainly increases knowledge of the English language but does not help EFL learners learn how to use the language. This theoretical knowledge of grammar rules, however, will be of no use to the students. Instead, pupils should be taught how to apply grammar principles in a communicative context. Innovative English Grammar Teaching Methods Grammar teaching refers to approaches, i.e. systematic means of teaching grammar, that are used to assist learners in developing competence in an unfamiliar grammar. The

following are some creative approaches to assist EFL teachers revamp their grammar teaching methods and make their classes more engaging.

Making use of songs and poems. Songs are one of the most enthralling and culturally diverse tools that can be simply employed in language schools. Songs provide an alternate activity in the classroom. They are useful tools for improving learners' abilities in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Learning English grammar through songs creates an engaging and calming educational environment for students. They may encourage thorough listening as well as creativity and use of imagination in a casual educational setting.

The following are some unique approaches to assist EFL teachers revamp their grammar teaching methods and make their classes more engaging.

Songs are one of the most fascinating and culturally diverse tools that may be used in language schools. Songs provide an alternate activity in the classroom. They are useful tools for improving students' listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. They are authentic and meaningful materials that tell a story, provide life insights, or present cultural ideas. They can also be used to teach a wide range of language skills, such as pronunciation, vocabulary, sentence patterns, and so on. Learning English grammar through songs creates an engaging and calming educational environment for students. They may foster prolonged and deep listening while also inspiring creativity and the use of imagination in a casual classroom setting.

Poems, like music, have significant linguistic significance because they convey authenticity and cultural perspectives. Poems successfully contextualise a grammatical instruction. They are a good tool for learning a given grammatical structure, specifically a poem exemplifying a specific pattern, such as jazz chants.

When presenting a poem to students, it is best to elicit the students' primary responses after the poem has been read at least twice.

Following that, after presenting the poem to kids, they may be requested to read it aloud or silently. Students may be requested to rephrase the poem in order to practise the specified grammar point. Students become acquainted with the framework by converting the verse to prose.

Furthermore, students can work in groups and share ideas on some projects, but they can also participate in solo exercises that challenge them to identify their own unique meanings of a particular grammatical pattern in song lyrics, poetry, novels, and other literature.

Students' creativity can be encouraged by: (1) composing another verse of lyrics in the same mood and style as the original, either individually or in groups, (2) writing a response (a paragraph, not necessarily in lyric form) from the perspective of the person being sung about, or any other protagonist. (3) having

students work in groups to create a music video for the song, (4) drafting a diary entry for a character in the song to investigate the ideas and feelings that inspired the story being told in the lyrics.

Playing games

Using games to teach kids, especially young ones, is a highly intriguing strategy. They often prefer to play games rather than sit down to study. Traditional methods required that study and games be kept separate, yet the fact remains that pupils are more interested in playing games than sitting down to study. Learning through games is usually enjoyable for students.

Grammar can be learned via the games. Understanding the significance of a specific structural pattern and applying it in daily life is a challenging challenge, and games might assist students overcome this difficulty. Games like scrabble and housie were created specifically for this purpose. These games are all about words and help pupils improve their vocabulary. In addition to these easy activities, simple dictation competitions, synonym competitions, word puzzles, anagrams, and hangman can be played to assist pupils enhance their word database. One of the psychologist claims that he uses a variety of strategies and technology tools in his seminars to help pupils learn to use and integrate grammatical points and skills. The students are first introduced to a collection of expressions that allow them to establish communication with one another. They are then introduced to verbs and adjectives that are commonly employed to reveal nationality, occupation, personality attributes, and size). They get numerous chances to practise the grammatical point both orally and in writing. After some practise, the students are transported to the lab to finish the project using e-cards in a site during their lab hour. They use the grammar point to complete the homework after accessing the webpage. They must define themselves in an e-card to a new acquaintance in this situation. The e-cards are then sent to their teacher for grading as a writing activity.

Making use of tasks

One of these strategies is task-based language teaching, which teaches grammar through communicative use of the language. Essentially, it attempts to allow students to use the language successfully. Assigning activities to students can help them learn grammar. Introducing numerous tasks would expose students to the use of language in real-life situations by engaging them in a variety of activities in the classroom. The advantage of task-based training over traditional grammar instruction is that completing a language assignment is more like conducting grammar exercises in real life. The activities utilised in the classroom are classified as pedagogical tasks or target tasks. Pedagogical tasks are specifically designed classroom tasks in which students complete communicative tasks that are limited to the classroom environment. They necessitate student engagement and the use of

language skills, but the ultimate goal is to complete the assignment. errors are accepted. The activity invites students to help them learn anything on their own, and most of the time they have to investigate something, write something up about it, edit something that already exists, and link to the base knowledge and data. This increases their creativity and helps them overcome their challenge in developing something truly new. Invention is extremely tough, especially when pushed to do it. Students are not obliged to finish the work in this manner, so they can do it wholeheartedly and so fulfil the learning experience that can be received from the assignment. Another psychologist recommends various steps for teaching a task-based grammar lesson. They are as follows: (1) determine a purpose for grammar education, (2) define the requisite grammatical competencies, (3) introduce the lesson, (4) students complete the task- urge students to use language fluently even if it means sacrificing correctness, and (5) students perform the task. (5) Students Self-Evaluation- Allow students opportunity to reflect on how they completed the activity. Allow them to discuss the activity in the groups in which they completed the work. Students should write on how they achieved the linguistic goal, whether or not they employed the grammatical structures you gave, and what other tactics they used. Then, either orally or in writing, have the groups discuss with the rest of the class how they achieved their goals.

Using story telling

Everyone enjoys a good story. Stories are an essential component of language instruction. They give a realistic setting for discussing grammar points. It can be used to elicit as well as illustrate grammar points. Almost all societies have a long history of telling stories.

Storytelling is a versatile strategy that can be used as a convenient and natural grammar teaching tool. It is the strategy that helps EFL learners focus the best and that they like the most. Grammar points can be contextualised in interesting and amusing stories. At this time, the students can contribute to the creation of stories and participate as characters in them. They will also benefit from learning grammar through the stories.

Using alternative media

Learners' learning interests are piqued by media. Computer resources such as the internet and audio or video clips allow students to connect with and listen to native speakers, which boosts student morale. Using video and audio clips in the classroom encourages students to talk about anything they find interesting.

Songs, movies, TV shows, periodicals, and newspapers all play an important role in language improvement. Such materials can be utilised; nevertheless, it is critical that students realise this fact in order for them to assist students in improving their language skills. However, extreme vigilance is required. They

utilise colloquial English, which is grammatically incorrect in general, and do not employ that version of the language in everyday situations. Students, on the other hand, can frequently engage with songs and movies. They can learn the meaning of terms and how to use linguistic tools such as comparisons and personifications through them. These resources assist people comprehend why such tools are required, as well as how to use them. With these new ideas, the entire learning and teaching process is enhanced, ensuring success in efficient learning. These are some inventive and creative methods of teaching English.

Conclusion

To summarise, English grammar has been taught using the chalk and board approach. It must be taught in such an inventive and creative manner that kids will learn not only to speak, write, and listen, but also to communicate through numerous engaging activities that highlight form-meaning, mappings for day-to-day communication. That is the aim of English grammar instruction, and it must be used for that purpose. As a result, innovative ways aid in bringing about change, and most of the time for the better. It allows students to learn more quickly, efficiently, interestingly, and interactively, and it is the teacher's obligation to abandon traditional ways in favour of new and better methods for the benefit of the students. Using new methods for teaching English grammar in the classroom will help pupils learn the language more effectively. Grammar emphasis with a limited scope may be more effective; input enhancement may be more effective with grammatical features that are less essential for communication; output enhancement may be more effective with grammatical features that have many salient lexical forms; and learners in EFL contexts may benefit more from grammar instruction.

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